

RECREATION OF WORDS AND ARTISTIC PATHOS IN THE TRANSLATION OF ZULFIYA'S LYRICS

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Abstract.

Article describes the analyses of translation in lyric poetry, somefactual and conceptual problems and their solutions, description of recreation of words and artistic pathos in English translation of Uzbek poetess Zulfiya's works.

Keywords.

poetic pathos, factual, conceptual, complexity of the translation, originality.

In the modern interpretation of poetic principles, the main attention is paid to the retention of poetic pathos. Poetic principles with national pathos are reflected in the English translation of Zulfiya's works. It is known that poetics: (Greek poietike techne - poetic art) is the ancient rules of literary criticism, the science of language and the system of expression of works of art ⁶⁰. Poetics is the doctrine of a literary work, which was understood in the sense of the theory of literature already in antiquity, as an integral part of the theory of literature from the first quarter of the 20th century.

According to the scientific and theoretical views of the theory of fine art of speech, studies carried out to date emphasize the connection between poetics and the structure of a literary work. Illumination of science and its teaching methodological principles change with depends on the concept of poetics other in periods in different ways using the bride. For example, in the works of Gozal Umurova, Nazaryan, Hotam Umurov and other researchers present an excellent analysis of Zulfiya's work. In addition, an example of the Uzbek language is expressed in the studies of Suyun Karimov. We have studied this problem in comparison with theoretical sources, textbooks and manuals that have appeared in recent years.

There are scientific and theoretical studies expressing the views of world and Uzbek scientists on the poetics of poetic works, artistic criteria, artistic techniques.

⁶⁰Theory of Literature. M.: "Higher School" 1978. P. 105

Of great importance are the studies of Russian and world philosophers, literary critics, who conduct significant research on the problems of creative and creative psychology, creative individuality and artistic style, the theory of the lyrical hero, modernity and its artistic and aesthetic analysis. in the study of problems of poetic principles. The characterization of poetic beginnings in lyrical works gave rise to many conceptual approaches to interpreting the essence of the poetess Zulfiya's translated works. Among them in the dissertation: "sociolinguistic poetics" (A.D. Schweitzer), "poetics of creative interpretation" (A. Zis), "semantic poetics" (M. Polyakov), "synchronous poetics" (M.M. Bakhtin), "formal poetics". (R. Jakobson)⁶¹, "aesthetic progressive poetics" (A. A. Potebnya), "progressive poetics" (M. B. Khrapchenko), "generative poetics" (T. ⁶²Van Dyck), the theory of "poetic discourse" (V. V. Vinogradov). ⁶³. In connection with the poetic principles in the Uzbek poetry of the period of national independence, famous writers and scientists, philosophers and aesthetics of the world, in particular, José Ortega y Gasset, V. Wolf, Romain Rolland and T. Some scientific and theoretical views of Bart were expressed by the example analysis of lyrical works in the study of poetic principles (in the English translation of the works of the poetess Zulfiya, synthetism is a relatively small or historically established genre features of lyricism and lightness) "digestion" of other artistic units, that is, a certain stage of the syncretic process in the development of national lyrics was implied.)⁶⁴

Each lyrical work is a kind of independent poetic system. Already, such issues as the internal branching of the genre and the emergence of its new forms, the diversity of poetic principles, expressive lines, the author's intention, the epic chronotope, the epic plot, the world of images, the volume of expression are being resolved, find their explanation on the basis of the central concepts of the universal literature of Uzbek lyrics ⁶⁵. In the recent past, it was impossible to understand and explain the essence of the concept and images of Uzbek lyrical works (the harmony of the relationship between man and the universe, the concepts of the homeland and the Alps, characteristic of the epic series, myth and mythopoetics, chronotopic theory) based on the trinity of Allah - being - man. We also advocate typological research in the aspect of creative assimilation of traditions associated with synthetic genres of national lyrical art, such as miniature, theater, and cinema. After all,

⁶¹R. Jakobson R. Linguistics and poetics. M.: 1960. pp.123-211.

⁶²Khrapchenko B.M. Horizons of artistic poetics. M. Nauka, 1978. p.123

⁶³Vinogradov V.V. History is the word. M. 1994. 110 pages.

⁶⁴ Khrapchenko. Horizons of artistic poetics. M.: "Nauka", 1978. pp. 121-167 ; Theory of literature. M. : 1978. P. 107. ; R. Jakobson R. Linguistics and poetics. M.: 1960. pp..123-211 .

⁶⁵Vinokur G.O. Linguistics and poetics. M.: 1960. pp..43-127.

specific changes in the genre chronotope, composition, plot, world of images and expressive lines are the result of pluralistic (polydisciplinary) thinking of the period of independence.

It is emphasized that researchers of lyrical creativity at the present stage of development of Uzbek lyrics should be conditionally divided into two groups:

1. Writers indirectly related to the imitative stage of poetic thinking.

Writers Leading a Purely ⁶⁶Hermeneutic Direction in Poetic Thinking.

We emphasize that only writers belonging to the second group contributed to the emergence of new internal forms of national lyrics, original artistic expressions. Indeed, synthetism by its nature is not a phenomenon that can be explained within the framework of specific cultural-historical, artistic and aesthetic laws, but is a product of universal poetic thinking with a focus on essence. In the description of the philosophical concept in the works of Uzbek researchers, the interpretation of epic and mythopoetic works is expressed, although not on the example of lyrical works. (M. Joraev, Sh. Turdimov and others) ⁶⁷. By comparative analysis of the English translations of Zulfiya's lyrics with other works, similar scientific and literary issues are clarified. When analyzing this type of laconic Uzbek lyrical works created in subsequent years, the following related characteristics are observed:

a) that the events described are clearly unrelated to each other;

b) the transfer of poetic principles of mixing reality and imagination, which are different from the point of view of the artistic chronotope;

c) the basis of literary montage in an artistic way;

g) speaking in the language of symbols and symbols in order to deepen the symbolic content;

d) opinions about the essence of life and the fate of mankind become a single whole in the personality of the author and acquire an artistic reality. The image of "road" ("yo'l" in Uzbek) is a find worthy of a comprehensive analysis. It should be determined not by its genre, but by its style in the system of modern images.

On the way, your eyes are impatience,

Hey mature beauty than the spring.

To my soul, your distress is offence,

For I know that love has parting.⁶⁸

⁶⁶ Khrapchenko. Horizons of artistic poetics. Moscow: Science, 1978. pp. 121-167.

⁶⁷ Uzbek language and literature. - Tashkent: 2005, No. 6. - B. 41-47; Kuronov D. "Mom's syndrome" in the literary process. - Tashkent: Akademnashr, 2010. 134 p.; Bakhtin M. Forms of time and chronotope in the novel. Essays on historical poetics. Translation from Russian by Y. Zhorakulov. - Tashkent: Akademnashr, 2015. p.16.

⁶⁸ Zulfiya. I was love. Poems. Translation by B.Kholbekova. Tashkent. "Akademnashr" p.21

Ko'zing muncha yo'lda intizor,
Ey, bahordan barkamol husn.
Iztirobing dilimga ozor -
Ishq hijronin bilganim uchun.⁶⁹

It is impossible to translate the correct variant of this poem without feeling or living with the author. Already now it is necessary to find a "key word" that opens the way to reflection, reflected in the axis of the artistic text, the problem based on lyrical principles, and its scientific and theoretical interpretation. »⁷⁰

Thus, it is appropriate to evaluate positively any talented writer's quest to interpret poetic principles to achieve maximum results with minimum means and refer to the judgment of time, how much the lyric work will be condensed in the future ⁷¹.

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⁷⁰Musaev K. Fundamentals of the theory of translation. Nauka 1988. S. 67-81.

⁷¹Vinokur G.O. Linguistics and poetics. M. 1994. 123-143